

Performance Evaluation of a SiGe Pocket Based Triple Metal Double Gate Vertical TFET for Low-Power Systems

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Abstract: This work presents a SiGe pocket-based Triple Metal Double Gate Vertical Tunnel Field-Effect Transistor (TMDG-VTFET) to achieve enhanced switching performance and low-power operation by a comprehensive assessment of channel length, pocket length, and gate oxide parameters. The Triple Metal Double Gate architecture is employed to improve electrostatic control and tunneling efficiency at source-channel tunnelling junction. The results indicate that a channel length of 20 nm combined with a 5 nm SiGe pocket region provides a trade off between ON-state current and leakage suppression, yielding a high I_{on}/I_{off} ratio of $\sim 10^{12}$ and a steep subthreshold swing of 20.39 mV/dec. Gate oxide engineering reveals that a 2 nm HfO₂ dielectric significantly enhances gate coupling, resulting in improved transconductance and reduced threshold voltage as compared to SiO₂ and Al₂O₃. Work function engineering of the triple-metal gate further refines band alignment, maximizing tunneling probability and switching efficiency. Temperature analysis shows stable operation at room temperature; however, the leakage is increased at elevated temperatures. The optimized SiGe pocket-based TMDG-VTFET demonstrates superior low-voltage operation, reduced power consumption, and strong scalability, making it a promising candidate for next-generation ultra-low-power electronic applications.

Keywords: SiGe Pocket, TMDG, Work function engineering, Temperature analysis, TFET

1. Introduction

The continuous scaling of CMOS technology has led to severe power dissipation and leakage challenges, primarily due to the thermionic emission-based carrier transport mechanism, which fundamentally limits the Subthreshold Swing (SS) to 60 mV/dec at room temperature [1-3]. To overcome this limitation, Tunnel Field-Effect Transistors (TFETs) have emerged as promising candidates for ultra-low-power applications owing to their Band-to-Band Tunneling (BTBT) mechanism, enabling steep-slope switching and reduced OFF-state current [4], [5-7]. However, conventional lateral silicon TFETs suffer from low ON-state current and limited gate control over the tunneling junction, restricting their performance in high-speed applications [8, 9].

Vertical TFET (VTFET) architectures have been introduced to address these drawbacks by increasing the tunneling junction area and improving electrostatic control [10, 11]. Further, performance enhancement has been reported through heterostructure and pocket engineering, where low bandgap materials such as SiGe are employed to boost tunneling probability and improve ON-state current [12], [13, 14]. Additionally, the incorporation of high-k gate dielectrics such as HfO₂ has been shown to strengthen gate coupling, reduce equivalent oxide thickness (EOT), and improve subthreshold characteristics [15].

Recently, multi-metal gate architectures have attracted considerable interest due to their capability to tailor energy band alignment and electric field distribution along the channel [16]. Dual- and Triple Metal Double Gate TFETs have demonstrated improved threshold voltage control, enhanced tunneling efficiency, and suppression of ambipolar conduction [17, 18]. However, a comprehensive exploration of channel, pocket, and gate oxide parameters in pocket-based TMDG-VTFETs has not been extensively reported.

Motivated by these observations, this work presents a systematic exploration of a SiGe pocket-based Triple Metal Double Gate VTFET. The impact of key design parameters on threshold voltage, SS, I_{on}/I_{off} current ratio, and transconductance is analyzed in detail. The optimized device achieves a steep subthreshold swing of ~ 20 mV/dec and an I_{on}/I_{off} ratio exceeding 10^{12} at $V_{ds} = 0.5$ V, demonstrating its potential for next-generation ultra-low-power integrated circuits.

2. Literature Survey

Adrian M Ionescu et al. highlighted the potential of TFETs for steep-slope and low-power applications by exploiting BTBT conduction [4, 5]. Subsequent studies on silicon-based lateral TFETs demonstrated low OFF-state leakage but limited ON-state current due to indirect bandgap tunneling[12]. To improve gate control and tunneling efficiency, vertical TFET architectures were proposed, showing enhanced electrostatic integrity and higher ON-state current compared to lateral counterparts [13, 19].

Heterostructure-based TFETs employing SiGe and III–V materials have been widely investigated to reduce tunneling barrier width and enhance BTBT probability [20]. Further, Pocket engineering has been introduced as an effective technique to suppress leakage current while maintaining strong tunneling at the source-channel junction[21]. In parallel, the adoption of high-k gate dielectrics such as HfO₂ has enabled stronger gate coupling and improved subthreshold behavior in advanced TFET structures [14, 22].

More recently, multi-metal gate configurations have been explored to optimize band alignment and electric field distribution along the channel[23]. Dual-metal and triple-metal gate TFETs have been reported to achieve superior threshold voltage control, improved I_{on}/I_{off} ratio, and reduced ambipolar behavior [10, 19]. The present work extends the works reported previously to further improve the device switching speed and other performance parameters by introducing Triple Metal Double Gate structure together with a SiGe pocket in the conventional vertical TFETs. The proposed SiGe pocket based TMDG-VTFET design dimensions has been extensively explored using TCAD tool which also provides insights into structural trade-offs and identifies optimal design considerations for enhanced device performance.

3. Device Structure and Simulation Setup

The device cross-sectional view of the conventional VTFET (reported) and SiGe pocket based TMDG-VTFET (proposed) are presented in Figs. 1(a) and (b), respectively. Silicon is used for all the three regions (namely source, channel, and drain) while the HfO₂ dielectric layer owing to its high dielectric constant value is used as a gate oxide in the conventional VTFET. The metal gate is divided into three electrodes, viz. M_{G1} (drain side), M_{G2} (middle region), and M_{G3} (source side) to screen the effect of drain voltage variation on source-channel junction. The channel is moderately doped (p-type) while the drain (n-type) and source (p-type) are heavily doped. The device design parameters of the VTFET taken into consideration are Metal Gate Work functions (i.e. W_{EF}); Metal Gate lengths (i.e. L_G); pocket length (L_{PT}); and Oxide layer thickness (i.e. t_{ox}). The chosen values of device design parameters are summarised in Table 1. The simulation parameters and physical models for the SiGe pocket based TMDG-VTFET are taken to be same as that of a conventional VTFET [9, 24]. The device characteristic is first calibrated as shown in Fig.1(c) with the reported work of conventional VTFET[25] by extracting the current with the help of Plot Digitizer tool. The generations and recombination of the charge carriers at the semiconductor-semiconductor and semiconductor-insulator interfaces are modelled with SRH (Shockley–Read Hall) model [26]. Further, the tunneling of the electrons is estimated using the non-local BTBT model. The newton trap method is invoked as a solution method.

Table 1 Device design parameters selected for the proposed SiGe pocket based TMDG-VTFET

Design Parameters	Values
Concentration Source Doping N_S [p-type]	$5 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$
Concentration Channel Doping N_C [p-type]	$1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$
Drain Doping Concentration N_D [n-type]	$1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$
Metal Gate Length1 (L_{G1})	7.5 nm, 10 nm, 15 nm
Metal Gate Length2 (L_{G2})	5 nm, 10 nm
Metal Gate Length3 (L_{G3})	7.5 nm, 10 nm, 15 nm
Channel Length (L_C)	20 nm, 30 nm, 40 nm, 50 nm
Pocket Length (L_{PT})	5 nm, 10 nm
Metal Gate Work function1 (W_{EF1})	4.3 eV
Metal Gate Work function2 (W_{EF2})	4.5 eV
Metal Gate Work function3 (W_{EF3})	4.3 eV, 4.4 eV, 4.5 eV, 4.6 eV, 4.7 eV
Gate dielectric thickness (t_{ox})	2nm (SiO ₂ , Al ₂ O ₃ , HfO ₂)

Fig. 1 (a) Conventional TMDG-VTFET (b) Proposed Device Structure of TMDG-VTFET with SiGe pocket (c) Calibration with Ref.[25]

4. Simulation Results, and Discussion

The detailed investigation of the effects of variations in metal gate work function, gate length, and gate oxide thickness, on energy band, surface potential, and electric field of the proposed TMDG-VTFET with SiGe pocket have been presented and compared with that of TMDG-VTFET without pocket (i.e., conventional) in this section highlighting the advantage or disadvantage of insertion of SiGe pocket at the source channel interface.

4.1 Energy Band Diagram

Figure 2 shows the energy band diagram of the TMDG-VTFET with SiGe pocket in the thermal equilibrium ($V_{ds}=0V$ and $V_{gs}=0V$), OFF-state ($V_{ds}=0 V$ and $V_{gs}=1 V$), and ON-state ($V_{ds}=0.5 V$, $V_{gs}=1 V$) conditions. Fig. 2(a) represents the thermal equilibrium state where no external bias is applied, resulting in zero net current flow. The Fermi level remains same throughout the device, and BTBT does not occur due to the absence of valence band and conduction band overlapping at the source–channel junction. Fig. 2(b) and 2(c) depict the energy band diagrams in OFF state and ON state, respectively, for varying channel lengths; Fig. 2(d) represents comparative energy band diagrams in OFF and ON state without & with pocket (5 nm) for a fixed channel length (20 nm). The total channel length is apportioned among the three metal gate segments as (i) 7.5 nm, 5 nm, 7.5 nm for $L_C = 20$ nm (ii) 10 nm, 10 nm, 10 nm for $L_C = 30$ nm (iii) 15 nm, 10 nm, 15 nm for $L_C = 40$ nm, and (iv) 20 nm, 10 nm, 20 nm for $L_C = 50$ nm. The work functions W_{EF1} (of M_{G1}) and W_{EF3} (of M_{G3}) are kept lower than work function W_{EF2} (of M_{G2}) for the creation of an in-channel barrier [27] which effectively screens the effect of drain voltage variations on the source channel barrier. The gate voltage effectively modulates this barrier height and therefore the drain current can be controlled. In OFF-state, the in-channel barriers at M_{G1} and M_{G2} regions increases the tunneling barrier width, and thus, restricts the probability of electrons tunneling. Whereas, in ON-state, tunneling barrier width reduces on the application of the gate voltage, so that electron tunneling probability increases as shown by dotted line of energy band diagram in Fig. 2. The region of M_{G3} with lower work function creates a downside band bending, which causes a higher electric field, specifically around the source-channel tunneling junction and thus shortens the tunneling width from source to channel. The energy bands under the electrodes M_{G1} and M_{G2} thereby acts as an equivalent band pass filter whose characteristics are controlled by gate voltage [27].

Fig. 2 Energy Band Diagram in (a) Thermal Equilibrium (Varying L_C) (b) OFF-state at various Channel Lengths (c) ON-state at various Channel Lengths (d) comparison of OFF-state and ON-state with & w/o SiGe pocket (5 nm) for Channel Length (20 nm)

4.2 Effect of Channel Length Variation in TMDG-VTFET Without Pocket

First, in this section, the effect of channel length (L_C) variation on the transfer characteristics, gate capacitance, cut-off frequency, GBP and TFP of the TMDG-VTFET without pocket are shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 3(a) shows the transfer characteristics and Transconductance for L_C varying between 20 nm and 50 nm. Drain Current and g_m are almost invariant due to negligible variation in energy band bending (i.e., tunneling area remains almost same) as shown in Fig. 2(d). However, other performance parameters do change due to variation in gate to drain capacitance (C_{gd}) as shown in Fig. 3(b). The high frequency characteristics of a transistor is defined by the unity gain cut-off frequency ($f_T = g_m / [2\pi(C_{gs} + C_{gd})]$) which is shown in Fig. 3(c) for different L_C . The f_T is higher for lower channel length (20 nm) mainly due to lower C_{gd} . Similarly, GBP and TFP are also higher for 20 nm as shown in Fig. 3(d).

Fig. 3 (a) Transfer Characteristics (b) Gate Capacitance (c) Cut-off Frequency (d) GBP and TFP of TMDG-VTFET without SiGe pocket

Table 2 Performance parameters of TMDG-VTFET without Pocket for Channel length Variations at $V_{ds}=0.5$ V

Channel Length \Parameters	20 nm (7.5nm, 5nm, 7.5nm)	30 nm (10nm, 10nm, 10nm)	40 nm (15nm, 10nm, 15nm)	50 nm (20nm, 10nm, 20nm)	% Change for $L_C = 20$ nm to 50 nm
V_t	0.551	0.546	0.544	0.544	1.27 (↓)
SS	36.57	38.59	40.10	40.53	10.83 (↑)
I_{on}	2.35E-5	2.41E-5	2.43E-5	2.42E-5	2.98 (↑)
I_{off}	1.19E-16	2.78E-16	5.51E-16	6.60E-16	454.62 (↑)
I_{on}/I_{off}	1.98E11	8.70E10	4.40E10	3.67E10	81.46 (↓)
g_m	1.18E-4	1.18E-4	1.18E-4	1.18E-4	No change

Table 2 summarizes the impact of L_C variation on the performance of the TMDG-VTFET at $V_{ds} = 0.5$ V without SiGe pocket. With increasing channel length, the threshold voltage slightly decreases from 0.551 V to 0.544 V, while the subthreshold swing increases from 36.57 mV/dec to 40.53 mV/dec. The ON-state current remains nearly constant at approximately 12.4×10^{-5} A, whereas, the OFF-state current rises from 1.19×10^{-16} A to 6.60×10^{-16} A; leading to a reduction in the I_{on}/I_{off} current ratio from 1.98×10^{11} to 3.67×10^{10} . The transconductance stays unaltered at 1.18×10^{-4} S, confirming consistent gate control in the proposed TMDG-VTFET. Percentage changes have been shown for the observed parameters for 50 nm w.r.t. 20 nm for the TMDG-VTFET without pocket.

4.3 Effect of Channel Length Variation in TMDG-VTFET with SiGe Pocket

A pocket of SiGe (5 nm) in the TMDG-VTFET has been introduced to examine the effect of pocket with channel length variation on DC and AC performance parameters as shown in Fig. 4. The variation in transfer characteristics and transconductance (Fig.4(a)), gate capacitance (Fig. 4(b)), cut-off frequency (Fig.4(c)), and GBP & TFP (Fig. 4(d)) are listed in Table 3.

Fig. 4 (a) Transfer Characteristics (b) Gate Capacitance (c) Cut-off Frequency, and (d) GBP and TFP of TMDG-VTFET with SiGe pocket

Table 3 Effect of Channel length Variation in TMDG-VTFET with SiGe Pocket (5 nm) at V_{ds}=0.5V

Channel \Parameters	20 nm (7.5nm,5nm,7.5nm)	30 nm (10nm,10nm,10nm)	40 nm (15nm,10nm,15nm)	50 nm (20nm,10nm,20nm)	% Change
V _t	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.53	No change
SS	20.3	24.3	27	28.57	40.74 (↑)
I _{on}	3.66E-6	3.74E-6	3.75E-6	3.76E-6	2.73 (↓)
I _{off}	8.54E-19	5.17E-18	5.03E-18	8.29E-18	870.72 (↑)
I _{on} /I _{off}	4.29E12	7.83E11	7.47E11	4.52E11	89.46 (↓)
g _m	1.73E-5	1.72E-5	1.72E-5	1.72E-5	0.57 (↓)

The threshold voltage remains approximately unaltered at 0.53 V for all cases, confirming robust electrostatic control of the Triple Metal Double Gate structure and role of SiGe pocket in the proposed TMDG-VTFET. The subthreshold swing is nearly ideal (20.3 mV/dec to 28.57 mV/dec) with channel length increase (20 nm to 50 nm). However, only a marginal rise in ON-state current from 3.66×10⁻⁶ A to 3.76×10⁻⁶ A is observed, while the

OFF-state current increases from 8.54×10^{-19} A to 8.29×10^{-18} A, leading to a reduction in the I_{ON}/I_{OFF} ratio from 4.29×10^{12} to 4.52×10^{11} . The transconductance remains nearly same ($\sim 1.73 \times 10^{-5}$ S), indicating stable gate control in the proposed SiGe pocket based TMDG-VTFET.

4.4 Effect of SiGe Pocket Length Variation in TMDG-VTFET with SiGe Pocket

The effect of SiGe pocket length on the I_d - V_{gs} has been found by fixing $V_{ds}=0.5$ V, and pocket doping = 1×10^{20} cm^{-3} , as shown in Fig. 4(a). The pocket length (L_{PT}) 0 nm, corresponds to that of without pocket case. The comprehensive listing of the performance parameters due to pocket length variation are shown in Table 4. The maximum I_{ON}/I_{OFF} ratio obtained is 4.29×10^{12} corresponding to the pocket length (5 nm) among the considered cases. As depicted in Fig. 4(a), the increase in L_{PT} leads to slight increase in I_{ON} due to increased tunneling area.

Fig. 5 Effect of pocket length variation on (a) Transfer Characteristics (b) Gate Capacitance (c) Cut-off Frequency (d) GBP and TFP of TMDG-VTFET with SiGe pocket

Table 4 Effect of Pocket length Variation in TMDG-VTFET with SiGe pocket with fixed $L_c=20\text{nm}$ at $V_{ds}=0.5\text{V}$

Pocket \Parameters	0 nm (w/o Pocket)	2 nm	3 nm	4 nm	5 nm	% Change w.r.t. (w/o to 5 nm)
V_t	0.551	0.546	0.546	0.542	0.538	2.35 (↓)
SS	36.57	43.21	43.78	43.58	20.39	44.26 (↓)

I_{on}	2.35E-5	1.77E-5	8.96E-6	5.32E-6	3.67E-6	84.38 (↓)
I_{off}	1.19E-16	6.71E-16	2.21E-16	1.91E-17	8.55E-19	99.28 (↓)
I_{on}/I_{off}	1.98E11	2.64E10	4.04E10	2.78E11	4.29E12	2066.67 (↑)
g_m	1.18E-4	8.69E-5	4.38E-5	2.55E-5	1.73E-5	85.34 (↓)

As the pocket length increases, the threshold voltage decreases from 0.551 V to 0.538 V. A significant improvement in subthreshold swing is observed, reducing from 36.57 mV/dec to 20.39 mV/dec. The OFF-state current drastically decreases from 1.19×10^{-16} A to 8.55×10^{-19} A, while the ON-state current reduces from 2.35×10^{-5} A to 3.67×10^{-6} A due to increase in tunneling width. Consequently, the I_{on}/I_{off} ratio improves remarkably from 1.98×10^{11} to 4.29×10^{12} , demonstrating enhanced switching performance with SiGe pocket insertion. However, the transconductance witnesses a decrement from 1.18×10^{-4} S to 1.73×10^{-5} S with increase in pocket length [19].

4.5 Effect of Gate Oxide Thickness Variation in TMDG-VTFET with SiGe Pocket

The gate oxide thickness and dielectric constant controls the gate capacitance as given by eqn. (1)

$$C_{ox} = \frac{\epsilon_{ox} A}{t_{ox}} \tag{1}$$

So, a decrease in oxide thickness increases C_{ox} ($=C_{gs}+C_{gd}$) providing a stronger gate control over the source-channel tunneling region. Consequently, the BTBT probability increases, leading to improved ON-state current and transconductance. However, thinner gate oxide also increases the total gate capacitance, which slightly affects high-frequency performance.

Fig. 6 Effect of gate oxide thickness variation on (a) Transfer Characteristics & Transconductance (b) Gate Capacitance (c) Cut-off Frequency (d) GBP and (e) TFP of TMDG-VTFET with SiGe pocket

Table 5 Effect of gate oxide thickness Variation for fixed $L_C=20$ nm and $L_{PT}=5$ nm at $V_{ds}=0.5$ V

Oxide Thickness \ Parameters	1 nm	1.5 nm	2 nm	2.5 nm	% change for t_{ox} 1 nm to 2.5 nm
V_t	0.479	0.512	0.538	0.554	15.65 (↑)
SS	27.31	21.81	20.39	29.13	6.66 (↓)
I_{on}	3.58E-5	1.05E-5	3.67E-6	1.48E-6	95.86 (↓)
I_{off}	4.20E-19	2.46E-18	8.55E-19	1.83E-18	335.71 (↑)
I_{on}/I_{off}	8.53E10	4.25E12	4.30E12	8.07E11	846.07 (↑)
g_m	1.32E-4	4.39E-5	1.73E-5	7.54E-6	94.28 (↓)

Table 5 summarizes the effect of oxide thickness variation on TMDG-VTFET performance at $V_{ds} = 0.5$ V, with a fixed channel length of 20 nm and pocket length of 5 nm. The oxide thickness is varied from 1 nm to 2.5 nm. As t_{ox} increases, the threshold voltage rises from 0.479 V to 0.554 V due to reduced gate coupling. The subthreshold swing initially improves from 27.31 mV/dec to 20.39 mV/dec at $t_{ox} = 2$ nm, but degrades to 29.13 mV/dec at 2.5 nm. The ON-state current decreases from 3.58×10^{-5} A to 1.48×10^{-6} A with increasing oxide thickness, while the OFF-state current remains relatively lower (10^{-18} – 10^{-19} A). Consequently, the I_{on}/I_{off} ratio attains its maximum ($\sim 4.3 \times 10^{12}$) at $t_{ox} = 2$ nm, indicating an optimal oxide thickness for improved switching performance. The transconductance decreases from 1.32×10^{-4} S to 7.54×10^{-6} S as oxide thickness increases due to weakened gate control.

4.6 Effect of high-k material (dielectric constant) in TMDG-VTFET with SiGe Pocket

The choice of high-k material (dielectric constant) also impacts the performance of TMDG-VTFET in accordance to eqn. (1). Increasing the dielectric constant enhances the gate-to-channel coupling, resulting in stronger electric field formation at the source–channel junction and reduced tunneling barrier width. Consequently, the BTBT probability increases, leading to higher ON-state current and improved transconductance as shown in Fig.7(a) and (c). However, the total gate capacitance also increases due to higher gate oxide capacitance; slightly affecting the RF characteristics as shown by Fig. 7(b). Moreover, Cut-off frequency, GBP and TFP also increase at higher dielectric constant as shown by Figs.7(d), (e), and (f).

Fig. 7 Effect of gate oxide permittivity on (a) Transfer Characteristics (b) Gate Capacitance (c) Transconductance (d) Cut-off Frequency (e) GBP and (f) TFP of TMDG-VTFET with SiGe pocket

Table 6 Effect of gate oxide permittivity variation in TMDG-VTFET with SiGe pocket for $t_{ox}=2$ nm and $L_{PT}=5$ nm at $V_{ds}=0.5V$

Oxide\Parameters	SiO ₂ (3.9)	Al ₂ O ₃ (9.3)	HfO ₂ (22)	% change for change from SiO ₂ to Al ₂ O ₃
V _t	0.655	0.599	0.538	17.86 (↓)
SS	31.38	25.74	20.39	35.02 (↓)
I _{on}	6.74E-9	7.45E-7	3.67E-6	54351 (↑)
I _{off}	8.67E-20	4.49E-19	8.55E-19	886.16 (↑)
I _{on} /I _{off}	6.97E10	1.66E12	4.29E12	6054.95 (↑)
g _m	7.07E-8	4.93E-6	1.73E-5	24369.6 (↑)

Table 6 displays the impact of gate oxide materials on TMDG-VTFET performance at $V_{ds} = 0.5$ V, for fixed gate oxide thickness of 2 nm and pocket length of 5 nm. Three dielectric materials—SiO₂, HfO₂, and Al₂O₃ are considered to examine the effect of dielectric material on performance parameters. The HfO₂ exhibits the lowest threshold voltage (0.538 V) and the best subthreshold swing (20.39 mV/dec), owing to its high dielectric constant and stronger gate coupling. The ON-state current is significantly higher for HfO₂ (3.67×10^{-6} A) as compared to Al₂O₃ (7.45×10^{-7} A) and SiO₂ (6.74×10^{-9} A). Even though, SiO₂ shows the lowest OFF-state

current (8.67×10^{-20} A); HfO_2 achieves the highest $I_{\text{on}}/I_{\text{off}}$ ratio (4.29×10^{12}), indicating its superior switching performance. The transconductance is also maximum for HfO_2 (1.73×10^{-5} S), due to enhanced gate control. Overall, HfO_2 (higher permittivity material) emerges as the most suitable gate dielectric for superior performance of TMG -VTFET.

4.7 Effect of Gate Metal Work Function Variation at source end in TMDG-VTFET with SiGe Pocket

Variation in the gate metal work function at source end significantly influences the tunneling efficiency in TFET devices as it directly controls the tunneling barrier of source-channel junction. A lower work function enhances the electric field at the source-channel junction, resulting in reduced tunneling barrier width and increased BTBT probability. Consequently, the ON-state current and transconductance improve, leading to enhanced RF performance parameters such as cut-off frequency, gain bandwidth product, and transconductance frequency product as shown in Figs.8(a), (b), (c), (d), (e), and (f).

Fig. 8 Effect of Gate metal Work function variation on (a) Transfer Characteristics (b) Transconductance (c) Gate Capacitance (d) Cut-off Frequency (e) GBP and (f) TFP of TMDG-VTFET with SiGe pocket

Table 7 Effect of Gate metal Work function (W_{f3}) Variation in TMDG-VTFET with SiGe pocket for fixed $W_{f1}=4.30$ eV, $W_{f2}=4.50$ eV, and $L_C=20$ nm at $V_{ds}=0.5$ V

Parameters	Work function W_{f3}					% change for W_{f3} change from 4.3 eV to 4.7 eV
	4.3 eV	4.40 eV	4.50 eV	4.60 eV	4.7 eV	
V_t	0.538	0.579	0.612	0.635	0.650	20.81 (↑)
SS	20.39	25.15	17.92	26.94	24.05	17.95 (↑)
I_{on}	3.67E-6	2.12E-6	1.05E-6	4.31E-7	1.45E-7	96.05 (↓)
I_{off}	8.54E-19	9.98E-19	7.23E-20	5.02E-19	1.10E-19	87.12 (↓)
I_{on}/I_{off}	4.29E12	2.12E12	1.45E13	8.58E11	1.31E12	69.46 (↓)
g_m	1.73E-5	1.23E-5	7.60E-5	3.73E-6	1.46E-6	91.56 (↓)

Table 7 illustrates the effect of source-side gate metal work function (W_{f3}) variation on the TMDG-VTFET performance at $V_{ds} = 0.5$ V for a channel length of 20 nm, with fixed $W_{f1} = 4.30$ eV and $W_{f2} = 4.50$ eV. As W_{f3} increases from 4.3 eV to 4.7 eV, the threshold voltage rises from 0.538 V to 0.650 V, indicating enhanced energy band modulation at the source-channel junction. However, the ON-state current decreases from 3.67×10^{-6} A to 1.45×10^{-7} A due to increased tunneling path, while the OFF-state current remains in the order of 10^{-19} A. The maximum I_{on}/I_{off} ratio of 1.45×10^{13} is achieved at $W_{f3} = 4.50$ eV due to trade-off between ON- and OFF-state currents, along with the lowest subthreshold swing of 17.92 mV/dec. The transconductance shows a decreasing trend with higher W_{f3} , reflecting reduced carrier tunneling at larger work functions. These results indicate that an optimal source-side gate work function is crucial for achieving improved switching performance in the proposed TMDG-VTFET with SiGe Pocket.

4.8 Effect of Temperature Variation in TMDG-VTFET with SiGe Pocket

Temperature variation from 250 K to 500 K is considered to evaluate the thermal stability of the proposed TMDG-VTFET with SiGe Pocket by investigating the variations in energy bandgap, tunneling probability, and trap-assisted leakage. Temperature directly affects the semiconductor energy bandgap (E_g) as given by eqn. (2). The bandgap decreases when temperature increases. A smaller bandgap provides higher tunneling probability and hence an increase in drain current as well as a higher transconductance is obtained at higher temperature as shown in Fig. 9(a).

$$E_g = E_g(0) - \frac{\alpha T^2}{\beta + T} \tag{2}$$

Gate Capacitance (C_{gg}) is less affected due to temperature variation as shown in Fig. 9(b). Figure 9(c) shows the variation of cut-off frequency with gate voltage at different temperatures. It is observed that the cut-off

frequency increases with temperature due to enhanced tunneling efficiency and reduced junction capacitance, resulting in improved RF performance at elevated temperatures. Figure 9(d) illustrates the variation of gain bandwidth product (GBP) and transconductance frequency product (TFP) with gate voltage. Both parameters improve with temperature due to enhanced tunneling efficiency and reduced parasitic capacitances, resulting in improved RF performance.

Fig. 9 Effect of Temperature Variation on (a) Transfer Characteristics (b) Gate Capacitance (c) Cut-off Frequency (d) GBP and TFP of TMDG-VTFET with SiGe pocket

Table 8 Effect of Temperature Variation for channel length (20nm), Pocket Length (5 nm), and gate Oxide (HfO₂) at V_{ds}=0.5V

Parameters	Temperature						% change from 250 K to 500 K
	250 K	300 K	350 K	400 K	450 K	500 K	
V _t	0.542	0.538	0.532	0.526	0.521	0.514	5.17 (↓)
SS	29.79	20.39	35.48	39.91	50.70	63.66	113.67 (↑)
I _{on}	3.26E-6	3.67E-6	4.16E-6	4.75E-6	5.44E-6	6.26E-6	92.02 (↑)
I _{off}	1.16E-18	8.54E-19	5.97E-17	1.34E-15	3.43E-14	7.14E-13	6.15×10 ⁷ (↑)
I _{on} /I _{off}	2.82E12	4.29E12	6.96E10	3.54E9	1.59E8	8.78E6	99.99 (↓)
g _m	1.57E-5	1.73E-5	1.91E-5	2.12E-5	2.37E-5	2.66E-5	69.42 (↑)

The present study reveals that TFETs show strong dependence of tunneling on temperature variations. Table 8 presents the influence of temperature variation on VTFET performance for a channel length of 20 nm, pocket length of 5 nm, and HfO₂ as gate oxide at V_{ds} = 0.5 V. The tunneling height and width decreases as temperature increases due to decrease in energy band gap, thereby, the threshold voltage gradually decreases from 0.542 V

(at 250 K) to 0.514 V (at 500 K) due to enhanced thermally assisted tunneling. The subthreshold swing degrades significantly from 20.39 mV/dec (at 300 K) to 63.66 mV/dec (at 500 K), indicating increased thermally assisted carrier tunneling. The ON-state current increases from 3.26×10^{-6} A to 6.26×10^{-6} A with temperature, whereas the OFF-state current also rises sharply from 1.16×10^{-18} A to 7.14×10^{-13} A. Consequently, the I_{on}/I_{off} ratio deteriorates from 4.29×10^{12} at 300 K to 8.78×10^6 at 500 K. The transconductance shows a monotonic increase from 1.57×10^{-5} S to 2.66×10^{-5} S, reflecting higher carrier mobility and injection at elevated temperatures. These results highlight the strong impact of temperature on leakage and switching characteristics of the proposed TMG VTFET.

5. Conclusion

In this work, a Triple Metal Double Gate VTFET with SiGe pocket has been systematically investigated for the effects of key design parameters including channel length, pocket length, gate oxide thickness, oxide material, gate metal work functions, and operating temperature and compared with that of a conventional TMDG VTFET. The device demonstrates strong electrostatic control over the channel region and hence, it shows a superior switching performance. A channel length of 20 nm combined with a 5 nm pocket region yields an excellent trade-off between ON-state current and leakage suppression, resulting in a high I_{on}/I_{off} ratio exceeding 10^{12} and a steep subthreshold swing below 20.39 mV/dec. An oxide thickness of 2 nm using HfO_2 as the gate dielectric provides optimal gate coupling, leading to enhanced tunneling efficiency, improved transconductance, and reduced threshold voltage. Work function engineering of the Triple Metal Double Gate further refines band alignment, with an optimal source-side gate work function enabling higher I_{on}/I_{off} ratio and lower subthreshold swing. Temperature analysis confirms stable device operation near room temperature, while highlighting leakage degradation at elevated temperatures. Overall, the proposed TMDG VTFET with SiGe pocket exhibits low-power operation, high switching efficiency, and strong scalability, making it a promising candidate for future ultra-low-power and high-performance integrated circuit applications.

Author Contribution Statement

Satyendra Kumar proposed the TMDG VTFET structure, simulated, compiled the results and original draft preparation.

Santosh Kumar Gupta supervised, reviewed and did editing work for finalizing the work reported in this manuscript.

Declarations

Conflict of interest: The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The authors declare that the data supporting the finding of this study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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